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THE ROLE OF GLYCEMIC CONTROL IN PREVENTING DENTAL COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES(REVIEW ARTICLE)

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ABSTRACT.

This review focuses on the impact of glyceimic control on the prevention of dental complications in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). Periodontal diseases, recognized as the sixth complication of T2DM, are closely associated with hyperglycemia-induced systemic inflammation, altered oral microbiota, and impaired tissue regeneration. Evidence from clinical and epidemiological studies demonstrates that improved glyceimic control reduces inflammatory mediators, enhances periodontal healing, and lowers HbA1c levels. Effective integration of periodontal therapy into diabetes management protocols has shown significant potential to mitigate complications and improve patient outcomes. This analysis underscores the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration between dental and medical professionals in addressing the bidirectional relationship between T2DM and periodontal diseases.

Keywords: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, glyceimic control, periodontal diseases, systemic inflammation, HbA1c reduction, interdisciplinary collaboration, dental complications.

Introduction. Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a multifactorial condition with systemic consequences, including significant dental complications. Periodontal diseases, identified as a frequent comorbidity in T2DM, are driven by hyperglycemia-induced inflammatory processes, compromised immune responses, and structural changes in periodontal tissues. These pathophysiological changes not only promote periodontal destruction but also impair glyceimic regulation, creating a self-perpetuating cycle that exacerbates systemic and local outcomes.

Emerging evidence highlights the potential of glyceimic control as a determinant in mitigating periodontal inflammation and its sequelae. Clinical studies have demonstrated measurable reductions in glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) following periodontal treatment, indicating a reciprocal benefit for metabolic and oral health. However, current clinical practices often overlook the interconnected nature of these conditions, resulting in missed opportunities for improved outcomes.

This review examines the mechanisms linking glyceimic control and dental health, evaluates the evidence for therapeutic interventions, and proposes strategies for integrating periodontal care

into the broader management of T2DM. The findings aim to underscore the critical importance of an interdisciplinary approach in addressing these interrelated conditions.

Materials and Methods. Relevant sources were identified through PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases using specific search terms such as “Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus,” “glycemic control,” “periodontal diseases,” and “HbA1c.” The selected publications included original research, clinical trials, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses.

A total of 68 studies were analyzed, including 23 regional and 45 international sources. Inclusion criteria were studies that provided evidence on the impact of hyperglycemia on periodontal tissue, the efficacy of periodontal interventions in improving glycemic parameters, and the underlying mechanisms of these interactions. Excluded were studies with small sample sizes, insufficient methodological rigor, or those lacking focus on the central theme of this review.

The methodology included identifying consistent data on inflammatory markers, microbiota changes, and the influence of glycemic control on periodontal outcomes. Particular attention was given to clinical studies that demonstrated quantitative changes in glycosylated hemoglobin levels following periodontal treatment and their implications for metabolic health. Data synthesis was structured to evaluate the role of interdisciplinary management strategies in improving outcomes for T2DM patients with dental complications.

Review of Literature Sources. According to the literature, inflammatory periodontal diseases are recognized as the sixth complication of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), alongside neuropathy, nephropathy, retinopathy, and micro- and macrovascular disorders [1]. In 1998, the American Diabetes Association (ADA) reported that periodontitis is more severe and prevalent in patients with diabetes compared to those without the condition [2]. By 2018, the ADA emphasized that periodontal diseases adversely impact glycemic control in individuals with diabetes [3].

Periodontitis is a chronic inflammatory condition characterized by progressive destruction of the tooth attachment apparatus. If untreated, it can result in the loss of supportive structures and eventual tooth loss. The prevalence of periodontitis is significantly high, with severe forms affecting 10–15% of the adult population and moderate forms impacting 40–60%. In its early stages, periodontal diseases often lack pronounced symptoms, complicating timely diagnosis and treatment. Moreover, periodontitis significantly reduces the quality of life for affected individuals [4, 5].

The multifactorial etiology of periodontitis, as proposed by Clarke and Hirsch, encompasses microorganisms, individual predispositions, environmental factors, and systemic conditions. Risk factors include smoking, diabetes, stress, neutrophil dysfunction, hyperlipidemia, hormonal imbalances, socioeconomic status, oral hygiene, diet, and alcohol consumption. A critical factor in the progression of periodontal diseases is an atypical inflammatory response, characterized by excessive activity of proteolytic enzymes in the periodontal soft tissues. The combination of these risk factors varies among individuals and changes across different age groups [6].

In the context of T2DM, hyperglycemia exacerbates these processes by promoting systemic inflammation and impairing tissue regeneration, making effective glycemic control essential in preventing periodontal complications.

It has been established that the majority of patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) develop periodontal diseases, while 10% of individuals with periodontal pathology are diagnosed with diabetes. According to the scientific literature, T2DM is a significant etiopathogenic factor in the development of conditions such as gingivitis, periodontitis, periradicular inflammatory lesions, xerostomia, alterations in salivary composition, and lesions of the oral mucosa. Strong evidence links periodontitis with glycemic status, as reflected by markers such as glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c), fasting blood glucose levels, and glucose tolerance test results, even in individuals without overt diabetes. Patients with periodontitis consistently demonstrate higher HbA1c levels compared to those with healthy periodontal tissues [7-9].

The model of the relationship between periodontal diseases and T2DM, described by Grossi S.G. and Genco R.J. (1998), highlights a bidirectional interaction. In cases of uncontrolled T2DM, elevated levels of systemic inflammatory markers, such as C-reactive protein, fibrinogen, and cytokines, impair immune responses and tissue repair capabilities. Consequently, periodontal

inflammation progresses rapidly, leading to tooth loss. Conversely, advanced periodontal disease exacerbates glycemic dysregulation, promotes systemic inflammation, and worsens diabetes severity [11]. This dynamic increases the likelihood of subclinical atherosclerosis, coronary artery disease, myocardial infarction, stroke, and mortality due to ischemic heart disease and nephropathy [12-14].

Hyperglycemia triggers a range of pro-inflammatory effects that impact multiple organ systems, including periodontal tissues. Adipokines secreted by adipose tissue, such as tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and leptin, play a critical role. In inflamed periodontal tissues, the levels of systemic inflammatory mediators such as TNF- α , IL-6, IL-1 β , prostaglandin E2, and matrix metalloproteinases are elevated. These mediators contribute to insulin resistance, pancreatic β -cell dysfunction, and apoptosis, ultimately impairing glycemic control in diabetic patients. Destructive changes in periodontal tissues are associated with glycemic variability and HbA1c levels. For instance, patients with HbA1c levels exceeding 8% exhibit twice the concentration of IL-1 β compared to those with HbA1c below 8% [3, 14].

Elevated blood glucose levels disrupt the trophic functions of periodontal tissues. Clinical studies and animal experiments demonstrate that the formation of advanced glycation end-products (AGEs) induces inflammation and tissue destruction in the periodontium. Collagen regeneration and basal membrane repair are significantly slowed, while AGEs accumulate in these structures, further aggravating periodontal tissue damage [17].

The etiology of periodontal diseases is multifactorial, involving environmental, microbial, systemic, and genetic risk factors that influence individual susceptibility. The primary etiological factor in periodontal disease is the formation of dental plaque, an accumulation of microorganisms that elicits a chronic immune response [18]. According to the literature, the composition of oral microbiota in patients with periodontitis is similar regardless of the level of glycemic control, but the proportions of specific colonies differ. The prevalence of TM7, *Aggregatibacter*, *Neisseria*, *Gemella*, *Eikenella*, *Selenomonas*, *Actinomyces*, *Capnocytophaga*, *Fusobacterium*, *Veillonella*, and *Streptococcus* genera increases, while *Porphyromonas*, *Filifactor*, *Eubacterium*, *Synergistetes*, *Tannerella*, and *Treponema* genera decrease. Changes in the oral microbiome create a vicious cycle: pathogenic microbiota increase tissue insulin resistance, worsening metabolic control. Simultaneously, elevated glucose concentration in gingival crevicular fluid, along with impaired neutrophil adhesion, chemotaxis, and phagocytosis, characteristic of diabetes, promotes the proliferation and persistence of subgingival microorganisms [15, 16].

Initial studies on the association between T2DM and periodontal diseases were conducted among the Pima Indians in Arizona, a population with the highest prevalence of T2DM globally. Emrich L.J. et al. analyzed 3,219 individuals, 45% of whom had T2DM, and found that the prevalence of periodontitis was three times higher in all age groups under 55 years among those with diabetes compared to non-diabetic individuals. Additionally, diabetes was associated with a higher incidence of infectious periodontal lesions, severe disease with deep periodontal pockets, tooth mobility, and recurrent periodontal abscesses. However, this study did not account for the glycemic control levels in the participants [17]. Taylor G.W. et al. subsequently demonstrated that poorly controlled diabetes was associated with more severe periodontitis compared to well-controlled diabetes. This study was among the first to highlight the increased risk of poor glycemic control in patients with both T2DM and periodontitis. However, the non-representative nature of the Pima population limits the generalizability of these findings [18].

Subsequent research confirmed that, like other complications of diabetes, periodontal diseases are strongly influenced by glycemic control. Patients with poorly managed blood glucose levels experience more severe periodontal destruction, often leading to tooth loss, compared to individuals with better glycemic control. Biochemical studies reveal that these factors correlate with blood glucose concentration and can be modulated through appropriate therapy. Improved glycemic control partially restores compromised functions, and patients with well-controlled diabetes exhibit periodontal disease prevalence similar to non-diabetic individuals [12, 13, 19, 20].

Several meta-analyses have demonstrated that effective periodontal therapy can reduce HbA1c levels by 0.27% (95% CI: -0.46, -0.07, $p = 0.007$) to 1.03% (95% CI: 0.36, 1.70, $p = 0.003$)

within three to four months of treatment. After six months, reductions in HbA1c ranged from -0.02% (95% CI: $-0.20, -0.16, p = 0.84$) to -1.18% (95% CI: $0.72\%, 1.64\%, p < 0.001$) [13, 21].

In 2007, the WHO Executive Board presented the final document of its 120th session titled “Oral Health: Action Plan for Promotion and Integrated Disease Prevention.” The report emphasized that most oral and chronic diseases share common risk factors. As with other major chronic diseases, oral diseases are associated with unhealthy environments and lifestyles, particularly tobacco use, excessive alcohol consumption, and high sugar intake. The report also highlighted the relationship between periodontal diseases, tooth loss, and chronic conditions such as diabetes, noting that the rising prevalence of diabetes in many countries may adversely impact oral health [22].

In 2012, the American Academy of Periodontology (AAP), in collaboration with the European Federation of Periodontology, published a consensus report highlighting the bidirectional relationship between periodontal diseases and systemic conditions, particularly Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) [21]. The investigation of this relationship remains a focal area of scientific research, with significant interest in the interplay between inflammatory and metabolic diseases such as T2DM and periodontitis [15, 23, 24]. On March 1, 2017, 15 global experts in periodontology and diabetes participated in the Perio-Diabetes workshop, organized by the European Federation of Periodontology (EFP) and the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) in collaboration with Sunstar. The workshop concluded that patients with periodontitis face an increased risk of developing prediabetes and T2DM. While there is no definitive evidence establishing a causal link between periodontal microbiota and diabetes-associated periodontal inflammation, recent studies suggest an association between altered glucose metabolism in carbohydrate intolerance and T2DM and changes in the periodontal microbiome. Experts noted that specific biological mechanisms underlying periodontal diseases could be controlled through effective diabetes management. Improving glycemic control has demonstrated benefits in enhancing periodontal health and overall oral status [19].

Patients with diabetes must be informed about their increased risk of developing periodontal diseases, which, without comprehensive treatment, can adversely affect glycemic control and elevate the risk of systemic complications, including cardiovascular and renal diseases [19]. Dentists play a pivotal role in the early diagnosis of diabetes through oral health assessments [25]. Oral symptoms and signs associated with diabetes include enlargement of salivary glands, orofacial pain, hyperkeratosis, erythroplakia, leukoplakia, oral lichen planus, ulceration of the oral mucosa, fibromatous changes, herpetic lesions, median rhomboid glossitis, geographic tongue, fibroma, pseudomembranous glossitis, dry mouth, elevated glucose levels in saliva, increased caries progression, periodontal diseases, gingival hyperplasia, recurrent periodontal abscesses, osteolysis, burning mouth syndrome, oral candidiasis, delayed wound healing, and an acetone-like odor in the breath [22].

Dentists should also recognize specific periodontal clinical signs that may indicate undiagnosed or poorly controlled diabetes and promptly refer patients for blood glucose testing and endocrinological evaluation. These signs include severe gingivitis and gingival hypertrophy in response to dental plaque, persistence of gingivitis and periodontitis symptoms despite standard therapy, progressive alveolar bone loss during treatment, and aggressive periodontitis in children and young adults aged 20–45 years [20].

Many diabetic patients lack preventive care habits, as studies report that 90% of adolescents brush their teeth only once daily, 60% do not use dental floss, and among adults aged 40–70 years, 54% brush their teeth once daily, 77% are unaware of their HbA1c levels, 42% are overweight, and 32% are obese [26]. These factors contribute to the progression of both T2DM and periodontal inflammation. A study by Elovikova T.M. et al. identified a significant correlation between poor oral hygiene and periodontal inflammation ($p \leq 0.05$). Using specialized oral rinses showed marked improvements in the oral fluid structure in hospitalized patients with T2DM after a treatment course [27]. Chicherina E.N. et al. noted that prolonged use of liquid hygiene products might disrupt the normal oral microbiota, particularly normocenosis, with anaerobic organisms such as *Veillonella* spp. playing a critical role in diabetic patients. Therefore, the prescription of specialized hygiene products

should be under strict professional supervision, considering individual patient characteristics and clinical guidelines [28].

Orekhova L.Y. et al. and Aleksandrova A.A. et al. highlighted the effectiveness of individualized oral hygiene regimens in preventing inflammatory periodontal diseases in pregnant women with diabetes [29, 30].

Conclusion. The interplay between Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) and periodontal diseases is characterized by a bidirectional relationship, wherein hyperglycemia exacerbates periodontal tissue destruction, and untreated periodontitis impairs glycemic control. The multifactorial etiology of periodontal diseases, encompassing microbial, systemic, and individual factors, highlights the complexity of their development in diabetic patients. Evidence from clinical studies and meta-analyses underscores the significant impact of effective glycemic control and periodontal therapy on mitigating oral and systemic complications associated with diabetes.

Despite advances in understanding the biological mechanisms linking T2DM and periodontal diseases, gaps remain in integrating oral health into diabetes care protocols. Collaborative efforts between dental and medical professionals are essential for early detection and comprehensive management of these interconnected conditions. Dentists play a pivotal role in identifying undiagnosed or poorly controlled diabetes through clinical signs in the oral cavity and ensuring timely referral for endocrinological evaluation.

Addressing modifiable risk factors such as poor oral hygiene, insufficient preventive care, and lack of awareness among patients with diabetes is critical. Targeted educational initiatives and individualized oral hygiene strategies, particularly in high-risk groups such as pregnant women and individuals with poorly controlled diabetes, can improve periodontal health and glycemic outcomes.

Future research should focus on elucidating the molecular pathways linking T2DM and periodontal microbiota, optimizing interdisciplinary care models, and developing evidence-based guidelines for managing dental complications in diabetic patients. Strengthening the integration of periodontal care within diabetes management frameworks has the potential to significantly enhance patient outcomes and overall quality of life.

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